

Evaluating Asymmetric Extraction for Optimal Orthodontic Outcomes: A Review

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Abstract

This article introduces a new approach of orthodontic treatment planning that is asymmetrical type of orthodontic extraction which is currently being practiced without effecting post treatment results. Orthodontic extractions have been an important key for a good finishing of the case and since the introduction of serial extraction I correct pattern of extraction has to be considered to achieve a balanced facial harmony. This article contains basic information related to atypical extraction and reviews about requirement of atypical extraction in different treatment modalities and its advantages and disadvantages.

Keywords: Extraction, Atypical extraction, Orthodontic extraction, Asymmetrical extraction, Orthodontic Treatment plan.

Introduction

Dr. E.J Angle expressed that to attain a desirable soft tissue, skeletal, facial harmony; participation of each dental component is a must¹. As the era of orthodontics is shifting to a more advance and unique approach to achieve a balanced facial harmony, a new approach has also been involved to this; which is Atypical Extraction. Atypical Extraction is “the unconventional extraction of the teeth other than the adjacent or opposite tooth to achieve desirable treatment goals”. To complete the patient's esthetic need and also getting the desirable soft tissue relation this unusual pattern of extraction is accepted. Premolars have been mostly preferred for extraction in orthodontic treatment plan as their site display the type of anchorage system which can be applied to attain desirable results². The premolars, lower anteriors, contralateral premolars, posteriors, and canines are the teeth that are recommended for orthodontic extraction in that sequence. In cases with Class 1 molar relation and Class 2 molar relation and bimaxillary cases to correct the angle of convexity the premolars are frequently extracted³. But in certain cases where premolars of either side/quadrant are already missing and severe crowding is present, in cases with carious pre molars, or ankylosed pre molars; in such cases the clinicians can get confused while proceeding towards camouflage, in such cases if desirable facial harmony is achievable after extraction of tooth other than premolars then atypical

extraction is an effective procedure. The treatment-planning procedure for patients who have either skeletal or dental asymmetries or both calls for significant inquiry in order to pinpoint the region or locations that are the cause of the asymmetry and be able to customise treatment methods accordingly. Additional considerations will help us determine when to carry out an uncommon extraction combination.

Review of Literature

Perfect symmetry is a theoretical idea that is infrequently observed in nature. When estimating difference between the both the sides, the ubiquitous phenomena of facial and dental asymmetry is frequently apparent. Lundström¹⁹ characterised the asymmetries of the arches as either qualitative or quantitative. Quantitative asymmetries include the unequal number of teeth on either side of the arch. Variations in tooth size and location that are linked to how the dental arch is connected to the skull and to specific teeth are referred to as qualitative asymmetries. According to Garn, Lewis, and Kerewsky⁷, usually, tooth size asymmetries did not influence a whole side of the arch. Teeth with identical dental asymmetry often belong to the same morphological class. The second premolars should align similarly if the initial right premolar is

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larger than the left. There were no statistically significant variations between the right and left sides of 500 dental casts when Melgaço et al.²⁰ examined mesiodistal dimensions of secondary teeth (apart from third molars).

Other authors discovered comparable outcomes^{8,9}. Therefore, tooth extraction should be considered as a therapeutic option in situations of qualitative or quantitative asymmetries in order to establish face balance and occlusion stability at the conclusion of the therapy. Orthodontists still struggle with tooth extraction, especially when deciding which tooth needs to be removed.¹⁰ The importance of the plaster casts for planning treatment orthodontically is emphasised by Rheude et al.¹¹ in order to perform asymmetric extractions in these circumstances.

Factors responsible for Atypical/Asymmetric extraction

1. Permanent ankylosis due to trauma.
2. Carious tooth other than pre-molars.
3. Tooth avulsion and implant failure on front tooth.
4. Tooth size asymmetries (Eg: Left or right side tooth are different in size).⁴
5. Upper and lower severe arch length difference.⁵
6. Microdontia
7. Facial and dental midline shift.
8. Impacted tooth unilaterally.

Extraction of the following teeth will help us determine when to carry out an asymmetrical extraction.

A. Premolars

Severe midline deviation or discrepancy in molar relation are most frequent conditions that call for premolar extractions. First premolar extraction is permitted by the adequate mesiodistal crown diameter because the resulting space can be immediately put to use in order to support orthodontic tooth movement with biomechanics for alignment and adequate retraction of teeth. Ginely et al.⁶ came to the conclusion that removing first premolars would make controlling anchorage easier and be very helpful in maintaining the proximity between the 2nd premolar and the 1st molar.⁷ First premolar extraction is recommended when there is a significant arch disparity in the anterior teeth, and unilateral extraction of second premolars is advantageous when the molar relationship needs to be fixed in order to address the midline discrepancy.

B. Mandibular Anteriors

According to Rheude et al.¹¹ asymmetric extractions must be performed on research models in order for orthodontic treatment to be successful. In other words, mandibular incisors may be extracted if there is a TTM and archlength difference of more than 5 mm in the front area. The disparity in anterior Bolton is a clear indication of extraction¹²⁻¹⁴. Riedel et al.¹⁵ state that another criteria emphasises the mandibular anterior tooth material more so than the maxillary anteriors, which is the standard procedure for mandibular incisor extraction. According to Miller et al.¹⁶ and Reidel et al.¹⁵, the treatment stability is increased with retention in the inter-canine width. In situations of moderate to severe crowding, an incisor extraction will retain the arch shape without mistakenly

altering the intercanine width. An effective torque control and proper monitoring, maintain the inter-canine breadth by preventing inclination of the mandibular canine while maintaining axial inclination of the mandibular teeth¹⁷⁻¹⁹. However, mandibular incisor extraction is linked to the development of black triangles as a result of a papillary defect.^{17,20,21} Lower anterior extraction shouldn't be done on a class 2 patient, as proposed by Bahreman et al and other writers, as it would cause an unacceptable overjet^{21,22,23}. On the other hand, it would be advantageous to extract the mandibular anteriors in moderate class 3 instance.²⁴

C. Maxillary Anteriors

During orthodontic treatment the extraction of maxillary anteriors is extremely rare. However, when a central incisor is diagnosed with a bad prognosis, it might be because of deformity or just because it is severely deteriorated and has sustained permanent harm²⁵. The space needs, form, size, and height of the root of maxillary anteriors, as well as their relationship to the maxillary central incisors, will also be taken into consideration.²⁶⁻³¹ The most frequent reason for removing maxillary lateral incisors is tooth agenesis²⁹.

D. Posterior Tooth Extraction

Molars are the foremost secondary teeth to emerge and have the posterior location necessary for mastication makes them most vulnerable to injury.^{32,33}. De Oliveiraa et al. claim that extraction of posterior teeth are effective for treating vertical development issues and achieving a class I molar relationship at the conclusion of therapy.³⁴ Some of the other writers suggested searching for symptoms indicating first molars should be removed, such as major caries, apical illnesses, severe crowding in the rear, and an anterior open bite. But before having them extracted, it's crucial to be aware of the third molars' presence and positioning in the jaw.³⁵ When there is a requirement for large arch space and the preexisting first bicuspids are in good condition, a situation is created for the extraction of posterior teeth that are endodontically or periodontally impaired³⁶. However, it results in a longer treatment time and a tendency for the lower second molars to incline mesiolingually³⁵. According to Sandler et al.³⁶, the clinical consequence after extraction of posterior tooth is the migration of the teeth present posterior to the extracted tooth mesially, which results in the rotation of the mandible in the opposite direction and the cessation of the mandibular plane. Thus, only when there was bilateral molar extraction does the impact become noticeable. To correct a severe anterior cross bite or to reestablish the normal molar relationship, Lin and Gu advise extracting the second molars if there are third molars posterior to the second molars³⁷. Lower posteriors should not be removed, nevertheless, if it is impossible to seal the extraction site, as is the case with horizontal growers who have powerful facial muscles.

E. Extraction of Canines

The canines are regarded as the foundation of the dentition. There aren't many scientific research reporting

on the maxillary canine aesthetic value in the literature³⁸. There are obvious indications that extraction is required when the maxillary canines need to be brought into alignment³⁹. When doing so, the canine should be replaced with the nearby first bicuspid, whose pre-existing inclination should be adequate to provide the patient an aesthetically attractive smile arc while doing so. If a canine is positioned ectopically, there will be loss of attachment, which can only be remedied by transferring them to a location with stronger bone support.⁴⁰

F. Removal of Impacted Teeth

Mc Sherry⁴⁴ and Pitt et al.⁴¹ claim that impacted teeth should not be brought into alignment if they are at an angle of more than 60 degrees to the midline. Hence, such teeth must be extracted. This is also true of all impacted teeth, that put undue stress on neighbouring tooth and thus leading into root resorption. Therefore, that tooth must be extracted and should be also considered as a part of asymmetric extraction and orthodontic treatment planning. The most frequent occurrence of this condition is when the second molar tooth root is being compressed by mesially impacted third molars.

Extraction in Case of Orthognathic Surgery

If orthognathic surgery is performed on patients with asymmetric buccally placed teeth when the skeletal bases should be symmetric and aligned with the midline of the face, complications may result. Unless some type of asymmetric extraction pattern or mechanics is performed prior to surgery, a maxillary or mandibular setback or advancement, either from a combination of the two, will result in a facial asymmetry. One of the major goals of orthognathic surgery is to achieve a Class I canine connection, hence it is desirable that the canines be as symmetrical as much as possible before surgery as to allow for the optimal setback or advancement of one of the jaws. It also reduces the rotational unit which results from skeletal motion asymmetries and that can cause posterior transverse discrepancies after surgery that weren't there before. A straight setback or advancement during bilateral sagittal split osteotomy surgery protects facial features⁴².

Conclusion

According to the literature review, taking into account asymmetric extractions has additional advantages in cases with removal or either damage to least of the tooth structure. Accurate investigation results are necessary for effective treatment outcomes.¹⁶ Always choose the extraction pattern while considering the dentition's overall health and not simply the biomechanics of the simpler procedure.³ In order to achieve treatment stability, the inter-canine width must be maintained or altered only minimally.^{16,19,20} However, the treating orthodontist should have a good knowledge and control over the treatment mechanics in order to finish the case with the greatest results in terms of function and aesthetics, therefore fulfilling the modern standards of face-centered therapy.⁴² The enhancement of face and aesthetics is a basic goal of orthodontic treatment. Facial appearance may be judged more from a frontal than from a lateral perspective from a social standpoint. Although a wide range of elements

may contribute to face beauty, symmetry.

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